

**IMPLEMENTATION OF ONLINE MONITORING OF THE TECHNICAL CONDITION
AND SAFETY LEVEL OF THE TUPALANG RESERVOIR DAM AND ADVANCE
PREDICTION OF EMERGENCY RISKS**

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Abstract. The article examines the stability of hydraulic structures through a case study of the Tupolang reservoir dam in Surkhandarya region, based on scientifically grounded practical research on the strength of the dam foundation. Issues related to ensuring the reliability of the reservoir dam by conducting continuous monitoring of the dam body, assessing its condition, taking prompt measures in case of risks, and automating field observations are discussed.

Keywords: reservoir, dam body, piezometer, water level, cavitation and vibration in the dam, infiltration process, online monitoring, hydraulic structures, emergency situation, monitoring, dam safety.

Ensuring the stability of hydraulic structures, which are considered potentially hazardous facilities, is of great importance in terms of improving the effectiveness of organizational and practical measures carried out systematically to ensure their safe operation. For this reason, in order to predict the stability of hydraulic structures in our country, the strength of the foundation of the Topalang reservoir dam, built in the Surkhandarya region, was studied on the basis of scientifically grounded practical research.

The part of a hydraulic structure with the highest risk of emergency is its dam. Ensuring the reliability of the dam requires continuous observation, monitoring of its condition, taking prompt measures in case of danger, and automating field monitoring processes. Issues of dam safety do

not end at the stage of site selection, design, or construction, but continue throughout the entire period of operation. Monitoring the condition of any dam is carried out by collecting data from all instruments installed, or to be installed, on the dam in order to observe its response to acting forces and environmental conditions.

To determine the condition of any dam's spillways, it is essential to use measuring instruments and relate the results to variations in the water level, which represents the primary issue of dam safety. In addition, in earth dams it is necessary to measure pore water pressure and overall soil pressure, while in concrete dams temperature monitoring, uplift and displacement measurements, as well as stress and deformation measurements, can provide a clear understanding of what is occurring within the dam and/or its foundation.

The monitoring and measuring devices are installed taking into account the engineering–geological and hydrogeological conditions of the hydraulic structure, as well as the type, height, and purpose of the pressure structures. Instruments designed for continuous monitoring of the structures during construction and operation are placed along the entire front of the structure, considering both the design features of the construction and the geological characteristics of the site. The monitoring and measuring devices serve to control the conditions illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Aspects monitored by the device in earth dams. During the construction of the hydraulic structures at the Topalang Reservoir, emergency repair valves and KRZ-2 control systems were fully installed, and both primary and backup power supplies were provided. Construction and installation works are being carried out in the ventilation section with the installation of collectors and automatic air intake and exhaust valves

1.	Solar-pannelled sluice
2.	Meteorological station
3.	Vibration monitor
4.	Single-channel data recorder
5.	Wire vibration crack detector
6.	Tiltmeter (Slope Gauge / Inclinator)
7.	Five-channel data logger
8.	Optical survey prism
9.	Temperature sensor
10.	Strain gauge
11.	LT-Inclinobus
12.	Soil Pressure Sensor yoki Earth Pressure Sensor
13.	Multipoint Extensometer
14.	Piezometer
15.	Strain Gauge
16.	InSAR

Figure 1. New methods for monitoring the main parameters of earth dams are presented

Based on the main principles of organizing special field observations and in accordance with the requirements of existing regulatory documents (KMK 2.06.05-98, KMK 2.06.01-97, clause 1.6), as well as regulatory-methodological documents and guidelines, systematic field monitoring has been planned. The purpose of the field observations is to ensure the safe and normal

operation of the structure. During the conducted research, the main tasks of the field observations were identified as follows: during the construction phase — optimizing the construction technology of dam elements and the reinforced-concrete screen; during the operation phase — verifying and refining design solutions by comparing observation results with the maximum allowable calculated control indicators; studying the processes occurring in the structure under loads and impacts during construction and operation; timely detection of defects; and preventing emergency situations.

Based on the conducted experiments, field studies provide effective monitoring. Special attention was given to the filtration regime within the dam body and foundation, filtration along the dam slopes, calculation of filtration discharge along the dam and foundation, overall deformation of the dam, rainfall, horizontal displacements, and the stress–strain state of the dam body and foundation soil.

Using this device, vibrations occurring in the dam due to various factors are detected online, and information is promptly transmitted to the monitoring point. Field observations include visual inspections at all access points of the structure, monitoring rainfall and displacements using geodetic methods, observation via geophysical techniques, and the use of control and measurement instruments. The stress–strain state of the dam and foundation, filtration and temperature regimes, the magnitude of seismic impacts, and the structure’s response are studied through engineering and seismological monitoring.

This device reports cavitation occurring in the dam due to the impact of water and allows remote detection when a risk to the dam’s stability arises. Using the sensors of the monitoring and measurement system, changes caused by landslides, earthquakes, and other forces affecting the dam can be detected online and remotely. Water seepage through the dam over time can damage the structure, destroy parts of it, and cause significant harm to agricultural and industrial facilities located downstream. Therefore, the management of water resources and the operation of dams and hydroelectric power plants is of critical importance and requires continuous monitoring. Monitoring earth dams is particularly important during construction and operation phases; sensors are installed on the dam foundation, lateral supports, dam body, and lateral structures, and the collected data is continuously analyzed. For instance, changes in the water level recorded by piezometers over time are used to plot the dam profile. Figure 2 shows the changes observed in the piezometer.

Figure 2. Changes in piezometer water level readings over time

The first step in monitoring a dam is to study the dam’s piezometer data. Over a certain period of time, the water level is recorded with the help of a catheter along the perimeter of the dam and its foundations. To obtain calculation data, modeling is carried out using the control and measuring equipment program installed in the dam, where boundary conditions are applied to calculate water level values in different sections. The program is a finite element software product that can be used to simulate the changes and distribution of pore pressure within porous materials such as soil and rock. Its comprehensive and large-scale formulation makes it possible to analyze both simple and very complex problems of water flow. For better comparison, the experimental results of changes in piezometer water levels over time along the transverse and longitudinal axes are presented.

This modern online monitoring device creates the possibility, in the event of a failure of the hydraulic structure dam or other emergency situations, to promptly and simultaneously notify all relevant sector representatives and the people living near the reservoir, as well as to quickly carry

out evacuation and implement urgent measures to eliminate the consequences of the emergency in a short time.

The emergency notification system at the dam is provided by the online monitoring device. To increase the reliability of the messages and prevent false alarms, data from at least three different types of sensors are used.

Control Center. When critical values in the monitoring system are exceeded, it automatically activates the warning and notification systems. The programmed automatic start-up system for operators at the monitoring site ensures high-precision safety. Electronic sirens: they generate high acoustic sound over long distances, provide clear speech intelligibility, operate fully during power outages, maintain complete functionality in extreme temperatures, have multiple power sources, and provide communication with the control center through radio and wired communication channels. Communication infrastructure: ensures communication between the communication center and other elements of the warning system, and makes it possible to connect the dam's nearby warning system in a timely manner to the main warning system. Notification of relevant responsible services: sends messages via phone or SMS to the agencies involved in eliminating the emergency and carrying out rescue operations.

During the conducted research, the following conclusions were reached:

1. The operation of the Tupolang reservoir dam under seismic impact was also tested. Based on this, the dynamic method made it possible to sufficiently analyze the dam's performance under seismic load and to determine its seismic resistance. During the experiments, special attention was paid to ensuring the durability of the dam depending on the nature of the accelerogram, the methodology of constructing the mass matrix, and other factors.

2. Systematic field observations allow continuous monitoring of the operation of structures, constant assessment of their condition, prompt determination of repair and restoration timelines, and verification of their effectiveness. In this way, at all stages of operation, the safety of the facility is ensured, and through monitoring devices, the stable operation of the Tupolang reservoir was studied.

3. Taking into account the importance of field observations for the safety of hydraulic structures, it is necessary to fully restore the design diagnostic control system. This reduces the risk of possible accidents and structural damage, optimizes their operating modes, ensures

effective implementation of emergency and repair work, thereby reducing operating costs and extending the service life of the structures.

4. Catastrophic flood zones, formed as a result of hydrodynamic accidents, and emergency situations related to the stability of the hydroelectric complex were studied. The area bounded by the flood mark was identified. Flood-prone areas, with a 5% probability of flooding due to a hydrodynamic accident, were calculated to protect the population and economic facilities.

5. With the increase in water depth in the reservoir, the roughness coefficient “n” decreases under average floodplain conditions. In winter conditions, with the presence of ice, the roughness coefficient was found to be relatively higher than in summer, and a constructive solution was achieved to prevent this. The main consequences of dam failure—catastrophic flooding of the territory, rapid inundation of the downstream area, and potential flood scenarios—were calculated and analyzed.

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